

CHARACTERISTICS OF A PENCIL PORTRAIT OF A PERSON WITH ITS OWN CHARACTER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7632413>

Abstract. This article is about the uniqueness of the fine art of pencil drawing and its drawing techniques. This type of fine art has been a close companion of people since ancient times. Because even in the Paleolithic period, which is one of the first stages of the primitive community system, people tried to describe their everyday life on cave stones. Starting with a pencil drawing of a human portrait with unique characteristics, we will try to cover the following topics and provide more detailed information about them.

Keywords: characteristic person, human drawing, lifelike, thin, old, bones and muscles, head, neck, shoulder, torso chest, waist-pelvis, charcoal, retouch, sangina, sauce.

INTRODUCTION

In our previous article, we covered the subjects of the science program in sequence. As a continuation of these topics, starting with a pencil drawing of a human portrait with unique characteristics, we will try to illuminate the following topics and provide more detailed information about them.

Drawing a picture of a person will be easy after passing the above stages of description and learning, that is, after mastering the basics of plastic anatomy. (Fig.1).

1 - picture. Bones and muscles of the human head image.

Because, as it has been mentioned many times, making academic images based on the living image of a person is done after a thorough study of the skeletal and muscular system (Fig. 2). In the initial stages of learning, it is better to choose a figure who is thin, old, with good bones and muscles.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Figure 2. An old man with a unique character.

Then, in the process of describing it, there is an opportunity to strengthen the previously acquired knowledge about bones and muscles, to apply experiences. It is known that drawing and studying a human image is first carried out in parts. It is as if a set of bones is studied in parts: head, body and movement - supporting parts. This is confirmed once again by the fact that muscles are studied and trained in this way.

We would not be wrong if we say that drawing a person's face and truthfully portraying it is one of the most difficult subjects in the educational process. Because a lot of knowledge gained in previous trainings is available to perform the tasks of this category (Fig. 3). If they are not sufficiently studied, the issues that are difficult to overcome in front of anyone will be transverse, slowing down the progress of the work.

Stage 1

Stage 2

Figure 3. Describe the human head in four stages

Illustration of a human head with a shoulder girdle

It has been emphasized many times above that the most important parts of a person's figure are divided into the head, neck, shoulders, chest area, waist and pelvis, as well as upper and lower locomotor organs.

a) picture

b) picture

c) picture

Before drawing their overall appearance, it is necessary to pay attention to the structure and shape of each of them, to draw separate quick drawings and to do exercises with auxiliary characteristics.

d) picture

e) picture

Figure 4. a), b), c), d), e). Describe the human head in four stages

Such preparatory work can be displayed in various imaging media. Usually, it is appropriate to use pencil drawings, especially charcoal pencils, «retouch» pencils and «sangina», «sauces» (pictures 4-a),b),c),d),e) shown above). Because with them it is possible to make pictures on large surfaces quickly and quickly, to express and show shadow-light relationships.

RESULTS

When using them, it is better not to use an extinguisher as much as possible. In addition, if it is learned gradually as a result of exercises, the responsibility for accurate work will increase significantly. The artist's confidence in his knowledge and practical experience increases. As a rule, before working on the full image of a person, its parts, i.e. arms, legs, torso, are practiced by drawing them separately from a living person. In this case, it is possible to depict a pair of hands, both together and separately, one leg or one hand, neatly placed on the surface of the paper. Every time they work, it is desirable that they are reflected from different sides, in different «rakrus» situations

As we mentioned above, during the organization of these performances, the models are used as thin as possible, bones and muscles are more clearly visible. It is possible to make his hand or foot stand in interesting compositional situations and make it meaningful.

First, it is studied how to depict the head together with the shoulder area, that is, the chest. In this case, it should be taken into account that all the parts to be drawn are expressively displayed during the compositional placement of the image on the paper level. In this case, not only the head itself, but also other components: the chest, neck, chest, arms and shoulders should find their proper place in the upper image. Sometimes the usual flaws are allowed by the draftsmen. They often start their drawing by sketching the head and in turn try to connect the neck and then the chest. However, every time the image begins not with drawing the head, but with putting the overall image into the correct compositional order and pattern, all elements should be depicted together. Some people, ignoring the other parts, draw the head first, place it in the middle of the paper, and then «attach» the chest, neck, and shoulders to it. In this case, the composition of the

picture will be distorted, the image will not be interesting. Therefore, he should first practice the work on small pencil sheets. Then you need to start by defining the outline of the object being drawn. As shown in Figure 5, it is very important to draw the general structure of the body (skeleton) of the nature, and the proportion of the body and head is very important.

At the first stage, large shapes of chest, arms, shoulders and head should be determined correctly in proportion to each other. If a part of the hands is included in the image, but not the whole view, it should not be allowed to appear inappropriately cropped.

DISCUSSION

As usual, drawing a picture begins with the orientation of the paper, i.e. holding it vertically or horizontally. Based on the side and height dimensions of the object being drawn, you can also choose paper in a square format.

Figure 5. A two-step portrait

All preparatory actions should serve the quality of the work. The main thing is the composition of the picture, it shows the way to determine the purpose. Figure 6. First, when depicting the head and shoulders, a person is selectively shown sitting in a calm, peaceful position. As a further exercise, it is recommended to work out the image of the head with the shoulder girdle and the chest in a dynamic position, with the head turned in relation to the shoulders.

It is known that the person selected for training should be a thin person or an old person whose neck, shoulders, and chest are fully expressive.

a) picture.

b) picture.

c) picture.

d) picture.

Figure 6. a), b), c), d). Shoulder length view of a thin man.

One of the pencil drawings should be continued in a long-term academic direction, with all its details, spatial, perspective aspects. Emphasis is placed on the specific characteristics of a person's body and age, on their similarity, and on the clear expression of the size of the forms. Each element is achieved in the overall picture and at the same time looks good individually. In this, the expression of shadows and lights in their place is also important.

CONCLUSION

During the exercises, the skeleton of the body worked in the previous stage of learning is kept, and it is advisable to look at it and model it on the drawing that is being worked on. Another exercise can be associated with depicting several views of the image on one piece of paper. In this case, it is appropriate to reflect the image in close-up, direct and «perspective» situations. As mentioned above, as a second option, it is also possible to perform the exercise of depicting the human body without the head and lower part of the body. Figure 7. In this case, the central part of the human body is the spine, the rib system, the chest, the waist, the upper bones of the pelvis, and the muscles.

Figure 7. Muscle movements of the human body from the waist up.

Hands can be taken and depicted in such a position that the wrists and palms are not visible. There will be an opportunity to focus only on the body part. Such a drawing is carried out in 5 stages as a long-term pencil drawing.

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